
FALSE IDEALISM IN MODERN CINEMA

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.7757398

Abstract:

Cinema is an audio – visual art. It displays the so-called realistic story and evoke emotional response of the spectators. This response is of course, aesthetic pleasure which is ideal. But modern cinema represents false idealism. The values of life seem to have no place in modern cinema. Crime is glorified and vulgarity is elevated in the name of art which is far from the ideal and the real.

Keywords: *Idealism cinema, Transcendental Idealism, Quixotic effect.*

Introduction:

The cinema is like a prism, the literature is like a sun ray. When it is thrown it reflects so many colors like ideals, trends, modernity, fashion etc. Youth is at the most vulnerable stage of their age. It falls for the things which have to be avoided in cinemas, where visualization of stories stays longer in our minds.

Discussion:

Fiction evokes emotional response to the story that happens with the fictional characters which ultimately result into the aesthetic pleasure. Who does not like the story of Cinderella? Who does not sympathize with the sorrow of Snow-white? Nearly everyone, the old, the young and the children love these stories because

of the inherent beauty of truth contained therein. Cinderella was compelled to do hard work. Snow-white was the victim of her step mother's cruelty and jealousy, but in the end evil is punished and virtue is rewarded. The readers feel happy at the divine justice. This is the ideal presentation of the pattern of life.

Idealism is of course a relative concept. The 18th century German philosopher "Immanuel Kant said that, "idealism does not concern the existence of things but that they are the essential feature of human mind. In his theory of "transcendental idealism" Kant says that the object of experience relied upon their existence in the human mind that perceives the object and the nature of the thing-in-itself is external of human experience. Reality is a mental construct closely

connected to ideas and therefore it is difficult to differentiate between true idealism and false idealism. Therefore it can be judged in terms of human values which are eternal and life giving and hence true. In this perspective we can say that modern cinema advocates false idealism.

Cinema is an audio-visual art. It influences the spectators to such an extent that they begin to project themselves in the role played by the main actors. The story displayed on the screen creates an illusion of reality and the young minds are impressed by the ideas and ideals shown therein. They project themselves in the image of the hero and do undesirable things in the name of ideals like Don Quixote. Cervantes the author of the novel Don Quixote has successfully shown the impact of fiction on the readers. Mr. Quixote read historical fiction and began to live in the world of chivalry. He imitated the life-style of knights and went on his journey to do the acts of bravery and chivalry.

It is something like the Quixotic effect of modern cinema on the young generation. The glamour and violence shown in the cinema attracts them. The majority of stories revolve around the subject of love, revenge and power. The Hero is either Gunda from the lower strata of society or a very rich and ambitious young man.

The heroines are presented as the showpiece in minimum clothing. They are living a free and luxurious life. Revenge is glorified. Nudity and obscenity are looked upon casually without shock. Cabre dancers are elevated and the poor young girls enter the world of glamor and money inside the Dance-bars. The cult of Barbala is emerged as the art. The dance was the thing of joy but now it is turned into showcase obscenity to gain popularity by doing some steps. The young women lost their self-respect in pursuit of glamour and money. The young boys incline to commit crime to get easy money. The movies like Dhoomor series like Money heist prompt the young men to thriller like robbery. The anti-heroes like Pushpa give rise to illegal smuggling. Law and order have no place in modern cinema. The image of the police officer is lower down. What is more disastrous is the presentation of powerful and corrupt politicians who take the law in their hands.

The rich builder either runs the Bulldozer or puts fire to the huts to vacate the place. The residents are helpless onlookers and the hero protests. But then the punters beat him severely. And finally, the hero becomes the Gunda treading the same illegal path. What if the residents protest collectively and if the police arrest the builder on the spot? But the things are presented in such a manner that it creates

havoc and anarchy in the society. Gang wars take place in reality.

Conclusion:

The values of life Mercy, Pity, Peace, Love and forgiveness have no place in modern cinema. These true ideals are suffocating in the glamour of false idealism in the name of reality. Art has its

own power to create revolution and peace or disorder. The one who present the art is free for creativity but when it is for commercial purpose or made for others it must possess some ethics that will help generations to move in right direction.

Reference:

1. www.wikipedia.com